

**DEVELOPMENT OF A WEB APPLICATION DATABASE FOR AN
ONLINE BOOKSTORE**

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Annotation: The comprehensive functions provided by the database system help to organize the activities of bookstores, to satisfy customer needs, to make quick and easy decisions, and to help business growth by saving time.

Keywords: An Internet bookstore, Database, Database systems, Online bookstore database.

Intraduction.

An Internet bookstore, or an online bookstore, is a platform that allows you to buy and read books online. These systems include collections of books, e-books, school textbooks, scientific articles and other textual works. Users can find, read and download required books through this platform. Database systems are systems that allow automation of data storage, processing, and retrieval. These systems provide database creation, management, and user access. The database is used not only for data storage, but also for data analysis, monitoring, statistics and other purposes.

Database management systems (DBMS) help to automate database creation, maintenance and processing. These systems allow users to search and analyze data. A database management system is a system that automates the creation, storage and processing of a database.

Database systems do not show the activities of various enterprises without an information system. These systems allow automation of data collection and processing. Database systems are a complex of programs and software designed for creating,

storing and processing databases. They allow users to search and analyze data. Modern database servers include all kinds of changes and mechanisms for high-level user interaction. These development tools allow users to create database management systems as applications.

Online bookstore database analysis includes:

- **Book information:** The database stores basic information for each book (name, author, year of publication, price, tour, review, rating, etc.). This information helps users search, select, and find books they like.

- **Customer Information:** The database stores customer information (name, phone number, email address, address, etc.). This information is used to communicate with customers and provide them with personalized service.

- **Inventory of books:** The database stores the inventory of books (quantity, availability status, purchase and sale prices). This helps to monitor the amount of books and their changes.

- **Orders and sales:** The database stores information about orders received and sales made. This includes information about books sold, quantities sold, prices and customers

- **Monitoring and statistics:** Monitoring and statistics are conducted based on the information in the database. It helps you define sales strategies based on sales, customer activity, best-selling books, most purchased books by customers, and so on.

PHP's Laravel framework based on the MVC architecture was selected for the development of the web application architecture for the online bookstore. One of the main reasons for this is that PHP is the best solution for getting new projects up and running quickly and in a short amount of time. In addition, there are also the cheapest hosting services for launching a project. Another main reason is that it is easy to create monolithic projects in PHP, and many components are already available, using which you can get the system up and running in no time. Currently, microservice architecture and monolithic architecture are widely used. We can see their difference in Figure 2.1 below. Monolithic architecture has a single database and a single application, its main

advantage is that it is easy to start small projects quickly, it takes less time, everything is very simply organized. If a project is large enough and built using a monolithic architecture, its workflow may become unstable.

Taking all factors into account, a monolithic architecture was chosen for the project, the reason for which is to get the project up and running faster, and if later the load increases, microservices can be considered. The advantage of using a microservice architecture is that the system can be built in small parts that are highly related to each other, even if one of the small parts fails, the whole system will not stop working. Other parts, i.e. services, continue their work. Each service is assigned a separate database. If there will be a lot of requests from users to a microservice, clones of that service will be used at the same time. copy takes over without any interruption in system operation. But it is not without its disadvantages, its main disadvantage is that it requires a lot of resources. In addition, the management of transactions between services becomes somewhat more complicated.

Basic concepts about the database

Nowadays, in human activity, the database (MB) plays a very important role in the storage of necessary information and its rational use. The reason: no matter what aspect of society's development we look at, we will definitely have to turn to the Ministry of Education to get the information we need. Therefore, it is a necessity of the time that the organization of MB is becoming one of the most pressing problems to be solved in information exchange technology.

The development of information technologies and the ever-increasing flow of information, the rapid change of information, prompt humanity to look for new ways of processing this information in a timely manner. The creation of MB for data storage, transmission and processing, and then its widespread use, is not relevant today. The work of finance, production, trade and other enterprises cannot be imagined without a database. The purpose of any information system is to process information about objects of the real environment. In a broad sense, a database is a collection of

information about specific objects of the real environment in a certain subject area. The subject area is a certain part of the real environment that is studied for the organization of automated management. For example, an enterprise, a factory, a scientific research institute, a higher educational institution, etc.

It should be noted that two important conditions must be taken into account when creating the MB: First, the type and appearance of the data should not depend on the programs that use them, that is, when entering new data into the MB or changing the data type should not require a program change.

CONCLUSION

The automated system includes essential functions for efficient bookstore management. By storing comprehensive book information including author, year of publication, and price, the database provides efficient search and selection processes for customers. In addition, customer information facilitates personalized service and communication, enhancing the overall shopping experience.

In addition, the database's ability to track orders and sales allows businesses to efficiently maintain transaction records, facilitating financial analysis and customer relationship management. In addition, monitoring and statistics in the system allows you to save time in the pre-sale process, set prices correctly, and monitor the level of growth.

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